

AMERICAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATION (AJMRI)

ISSN: 2158-8155 (ONLINE), 2832-4854 (PRINT)

VOLUME 1 ISSUE 4 (2022)

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PUBLISHED BY: E-PALLI, DELAWARE, USA

Extent of Awareness to Current Trends and Practices and Commitment in the Teaching Profession: The Case of Antique Public School Teachers

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Article Information

Received: October 05, 2022

Accepted: October 09, 2022

Published: October 13, 2022

Keywords

Public Teachers, Professional Development, Trends in Teaching, Commitment

ABSTRACT

The teaching profession remains challenging due to growing demands and the world's changing needs. However, the role of teachers has remained inspiring, requiring more service than employment for the sake of the youth and future generations. The study aimed to assess the extent of awareness of the current trends and the commitment in the teaching profession of public school teachers in the Schools Division of Antique, Philippines. The researchers employed a descriptive-correlational research design using a validated questionnaire in data gathering for the 320 randomly chosen teacher-respondents. Results revealed that most of the teachers were degree holders only, with less than ten years of teaching experience, and were dominated by female teachers. They were highly aware of the current trends and practices in the teaching profession and highly committed to their work. Results also indicated that teachers' commitment is influenced by their level of education. Teachers with a greater level of education are more committed to their careers. Teachers with higher educational attainment are more effective than those with a lesser level of education. Similarly, teachers with more years of experience teach better than those with less experience. Teachers' educational level and sex have little effect on their teaching performance. Moreover, teachers' performance is related to their understanding of current trends and practices in the teaching profession and their commitment. Therefore, the greater teachers' awareness, the more receptive they are to change, and the greater their commitment, the better their teaching performance and the tasks and responsibilities they may be assigned in response to changes in the educational system. The researchers suggest that the department shall provide continuous professional development interventions to give educators the tools and skills to stay modern with the needs of students and allows them to plan for changing trends in education.

INTRODUCTION

A profession is a vital social, economic, and technological endeavor. Teaching is a profession that emerges from social and economic changes in societies and has social, cultural, economic, scientific, and technological components. Teaching needs field specialization, teaching skills, instructional practices, and specific personal characteristics. Individuals who choose to teach must have subject matter knowledge, teaching abilities, and relevant personality attributes to perform their role (Hotaman, 2010). It is crucial to hire qualified and committed teachers in the field since education plays a crucial role in training future generations of any society. As a result, picking a profession in teaching becomes increasingly important. According to Ingersoll and Collins (2018), teachers are generally seen as the school's foundation; without them, there would be no school. Thus, comprehending the educational system requires an understanding of the functions of instructors. Typically, discussions of organizations include information about the roles that individuals play within them. The sort of employees employed by a company is a defining characteristic of its roles. Compared to nonprofessionals, professionals have greater control over their work settings, greater status, and comparatively higher income. This classification is typically at the center of labor issues and is not without debate.

Undeniably, teaching is a dynamic profession. Depending on the classes we teach and the number of students we have, it varies from year to year. But throughout the past century, the educational landscape has essentially remained unchanged. Our classes are still dominated by teachers. The teacher's job in a teacher-centered classroom is to impart knowledge to the pupils and assess their retention and comprehension of that knowledge through tests. Students who are passive learners do not analyze, apply, evaluate, or produce knowledge; rather, they just comprehend and retain it. Moreover, many teachers are beginning to assert that this way of teaching is no longer useful. They say schools need to change to prepare students for a world that is becoming more tech-based and globalized, where they will live and work. Further, the education delivery system influences learners' 21st-century competencies. Pedagogy, curriculum, school norms and atmosphere, assessments, and benchmarking are crucial to developing and monitoring 21st-century abilities. The classroom is where the above components come together to bring knowledge and skills. In the classroom, students can witness teachers exhibiting these abilities and practicing them themselves. Preparing and training teachers in 21st-century skills acquisition and distribution is crucial. Measuring classroom processes and teacher practices that support 21st-century skills can be the first step (Kim, Raza, & Seidman, 2019).

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The quality of education has changed a lot in the past few years. Before, the main goal of institutions was to teach students certain types of knowledge that they were expected to use later. Now, the main goal of institutions is to teach students “life skills.” Our goal is to teach students how to learn on their own and how to work so that they can come up with new ideas. One important part of modern life is coming up with new ideas. We need professionals who understand different cultures, are skilled, innovative, and creative problem-solvers, and can think critically. With the help of new technologies, people can learn to think more critically (Nessipbayeva, n.d). According to existing studies, committed teachers to focus more on their work, place greater emphasis on accomplishing school goals, and remain in school. In addition, it was revealed that teacher dedication was connected with instructional presentation, absenteeism, burnout, and turnover. It has also been shown to alter students’ achievement gains and their school performance (Park, 2005). As supported by Day (2008), committed teachers engage in communication with their pupils, take into account their growth, and meaningfully work to build their aptitude for a diverse range of activities. Thus, if educational institutions can make teachers more committed, there will be a better chance that these teachers will be interested in their jobs. So, if schools want more engaged teachers, they need to encourage teachers to be committed (Shu, 2022).

In light of the recent changes made to the curricula of basic education (elementary to senior high school) in the Philippines, increasing the research ability of teachers has emerged as a critical component in the process of improving the teaching practices of those teachers (Gutierrez, 2019). Indeed, one of the new trends that teachers must adopt is the use of Information and communication technologies in the teaching-learning process. ICTs are considered to empower instructors and learners, encourage change, and cultivate 21st-century abilities, although evidence is weak. There is a widespread belief that ICTs can and will empower teachers and learners, transforming teaching and learning from teacher-dominated to student-centered. This transformation will result in increased learning gains for students, creating and allowing them to develop their creativity, problem-solving abilities, informational reasoning skills, communication skills, and other higher-order thinking skills. There are few conclusive statistics to support this belief (World Bank, 2008).

With this scenario, the researchers aimed to assess the extent of awareness of the current trends and the commitment in the teaching profession of public school teachers in the Schools Division of Antique, Philippines. Specifically, it sought to answer the following objectives: (1) determine the extent of awareness of teachers of the current trends and practices in the teaching profession when they are taken as an entire group and when they are classified as to educational attainment, length of service, educational level taught, and sex; (2) determine

the extent of the commitment of teachers when they are taken as an entire group and when they are classified as to educational attainment, length of service, educational level taught, and sex; (3) test the significant differences in the extent of awareness of teachers of the current trends and practices in the teaching profession when grouped according to their profile variables; and (4) test the significant differences in the extent of the commitment of the teachers when grouped according to their profile variables.

METHODOLOGY

Research Method

The researchers employed a descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive research gathers, analyzes, classifies, and tabulates data regarding prevailing conditions, practices, processes, trends, and cause-effect linkages then interpret it with or without statistical methodologies. This method also determines prevailing facts in a group under investigation, which describes the group’s general characteristics (Calderon, 2006). Additionally, this is the most appropriate method for this study because it involves collecting data to test the hypothesis and answer questions on the extent of awareness of the current trends and the commitment in the teaching profession of public school teachers.

Respondents and Sampling Procedure

The respondents of the study were 320 teachers from the randomly selected elementary and secondary schools in the Division of Antique. The researchers employed a multistage sampling technique. The researcher opted to use the cluster sampling techniques for the reason that Antique is already divided into four clusters based on the number of students and teachers present for every cluster. It is assumed that the difference in the number of teachers and students per cluster does not significantly depart.

Research Instruments and Validation

The researchers made use of a constructed survey questionnaire to assess the extent of awareness of the current trends and the commitment in the teaching profession of public school teachers in the Schools Division of Antique, Philippines. The survey questionnaire has three (3) parts. Part I described the profile of the public teachers. Then, Part II assessed the extent of awareness of the current trends and practices of public teachers. While Part III of the instrument determined the extent of the commitment of the public teachers in their teaching profession.

Then, the instrument was subjected to a validation process. First, face validation was made on the research instrument by the experts. The revised questionnaire was approved after integrating their ideas. Cronbach’s alpha analysis was used to examine the questionnaire’s validity and reliability. Cronbach’s alpha measures questionnaire reliability. The instrument’s alpha value was 0.917,

which is excellent. Thus, alpha value reliability statistics reveal that all questionnaire indicators are good, and the instrument is generally accepted.

Data Analysis

Frequency counts (f) and percentages (%) were used to describe the profile of the respondents. Then, mean and standard deviation were used to assess the extent of awareness of the current trends and practices and the commitment of the public school teachers. On the other hand, ANOVA with a post hoc test was employed to determine the significant differences among three or more groups in the study. While a t-test was used to determine the significant differences between the two groups in the study. Finally, the data were statistically analyzed using IBM SPSS version 29.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Profile of Public Schools in the Schools Division Antique

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the profile of the teachers in the public schools in the Schools Division of Antique.

The table above shows that when the teachers are grouped as to their educational attainment, 147 or 45.9% are BS degree holders, 140 or 43.8% have master’s units, 23 or 7.2% are master’s degree holders, and only 10 or 3.1% have PhD/EdD units. As to the length of service, 153 or 47.8% have 10 years and below length of service, 106 or 33.1% have 11-20 years of service, and 61 or 19.1% have 21 years and more length of teaching service. As to the educational level taught, 149 or 46.6% are elementary teachers, while 171 or 53.4% are secondary teachers. Then, in terms of sex, 230 or 71.9% are female

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution on the profile of the public school teachers (n=320)

Profile Variables	f	%
Educational Attainment		
Master’s degree with PhD/EdD unit	10	3.10
Master’s degree holder	23	7.20
BS with master’s degree units	140	43.80
BS degree holder	147	45.90
Length of Service		
21 years and above	61	19.10
11-20 years	106	33.10
10 years and below	153	47.80
Educational Level Taught		
Secondary/High School	171	53.40
Elementary	149	46.60
Sex		
Male	90	28.10
Female	230	71.90
Total	320	100.00

teachers, while 90 or 28.1% are male teachers. Thus, it can be inferred that most of the teachers are only bachelor’s degree holders despite they have been in the teaching profession for more or less ten years, they are teaching in the elementary grade, and there are more female teachers as compared to male teachers.

Extent of Awareness of the Current Trends and Practices in the Teaching Profession

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation on the extent of awareness of the current trends and practices in the teaching profession of the teachers in the Schools

Table 2: Extent of awareness of the current trends and practices in the teaching profession of the teachers in the Schools Division of Antique

Variables	x	sd	Interpretation
Entire Group	2.83	0.406	Highly Aware
Educational Attainment			
Master’s degree with PhD/EdD unit	3.18	1.034	Highly Aware
Master’s degree holder	3.14	0.897	Highly Aware
BS with master’s degree units	2.85	0.564	Highly Aware
BS degree holder	2.73	0.237	Highly Aware
Length of Service			
21 years and above	2.86	0.456	Highly Aware
11-20 years	2.87	0.897	Highly Aware
10 years and below	2.78	0.356	Highly Aware
Educational Level Taught			
Secondary/High School	2.79	1.008	Highly Aware
Elementary	2.87	0.975	Highly Aware
Sex			
Male	2.83	0.784	Highly Aware
Female	2.83	0.801	Highly Aware

Legend: 1.00-1.50= ‘not aware’, 1.51-2.50= ‘slightly aware’, 2.51-3.50= ‘highly aware’, 3.51-4.00= ‘fully aware’ x=mean; sd=standard deviation.

Division of Antique. Data shows that the teachers in the Division of Antique have a “high” extent of awareness of the current trends and practices of the teaching profession

when taken as an entire group (x=2.83; sd=0.406) and when classified according to certain categories. Although the faculty rate themselves to be having a

“high” extent of awareness, further scrutiny reveals that in terms of educational attainment, those with the highest educational attainment, the master’s degree holders with PhD or EdD units, have the highest mean score ($x=3.18$; $sd=1.034$) followed by the master’s degree holders ($x=3.14$; $sd=0.897$), then those with masters units ($x=2.85$; $sd=0.564$) and finally those BS degree holders ($x=2.73$; $sd=0.237$).

In terms of length of service, teachers with 21 years of service and more and teachers with 11-20 years in service shared a slightly higher extent of awareness ($x=2.86$; $sd=0.456$) than those with a shorter experience of ten years and below ($x=2.78$; $sd=0.356$). With regards to the educational level taught, the elementary teachers posted a slightly higher extent of awareness ($x=2.87$; 0.975) than

secondary teachers ($x=2.79$; $sd=1.008$). As to the gender, it was revealed that male teachers ($x=2.83$; $sd=0.784$) have the same extent of awareness as the female teacher ($x=2.83$; $sd=0.801$).

The data reveal that the teachers are generally highly aware of what is going on in the system, the present thrusts and programs and the things that are expected of them, and the occurrence of the new technology that is used in the teaching-learning process like the integration of ICT and educational technology.

Extent of Teachers’ Commitment to Work

Table 3 displays the mean and standard deviation on the extent of commitment to work of teachers in the Schools Division of Antique.

Table 3: Extent of commitment to work of teachers in the Schools Division of Antique

Variables	x	sd	Interpretation
Entire Group	3.15	0.075	Highly Committed
Educational Attainment			
Master’s degree with PhD/EdD unit	3.39	0.866	Highly Committed
Master’s degree holder	3.25	0.904	Highly Committed
BS with master’s degree units	3.16	0.781	Highly Committed
BS degree holder	3.11	0.654	Highly Committed
Length of Service			
21 years and above	3.15	0.942	Highly Committed
11-20 years	3.18	1.006	Highly Committed
10 years and below	3.14	0.365	Highly Committed
Educational Level Taught			
Secondary/High School	3.13	0.895	Highly Committed
Elementary	3.18	0.883	Highly Committed
Sex			
Male	3.16	0.948	Highly Committed
Female	3.15	0.896	Highly Committed

Legend: 1.00-1.50=’not committed’, 1.51-2.50=’slightly committed’ ; 2.51-3.50=’highly committed’ ; 3.51-4.00=’fully committed’, x =mean; sd =standard deviation.

Table 3 disclosed that the teachers in the Schools Division of Antique have a “high” extent of commitment ($x=3.15$; $sd=0.075$). Although the teachers shared a similarly high extent of commitment towards their work, further scrutiny of the means revealed that in terms of educational attainment, those with the highest educational attainment showed the highest commitment ($x=3.39$; $sd=0.866$) compared to the master’s degree holders ($x=3.25$; $sd=0.904$), teachers with master’s degree units ($x=3.16$; $sd=0.781$) and the BS degree holders ($x=3.11$; $sd=0.654$). As to the length of service, teachers with 11-20 years in service posted the highest extent of commitment ($x=3.18$; $sd=1.006$) compared to those who have 21 and more years of service ($x=3.15$; $sd=0.942$) and those with ten (10) years and below teaching experience ($x=3.14$; $sd=0.365$).

Between elementary and secondary teachers, the result showed that the elementary school teachers have a slightly higher extent of commitment ($x=3.18$; $sd=0.883$) than their counterparts in the secondary schools ($x=3.13$; $sd=0.895$). In terms of sex, though both groups expressed a high extent of commitment, the mean scores

revealed that the female teachers ($x=3.16$; $sd=0.948$) have a slightly higher commitment than male teachers ($x=3.15$; $sd=0.896$).

This suggests that the teachers in the Division of Antique have a strong sense of duty and compulsion to address with passion the different works, programs, and activities assigned to them. They consider their work as something important and of value to them, as manifested by their high commitment to their teaching jobs.

Test of Differences Between the Extent of Awareness of Teachers of the Current Trends and Practices and their Profile Variables

Tables 4 to 6 present the test of significant differences in the extent of awareness of teachers of the current trends and practices in the teaching profession when grouped according to their profile variables.

As can be gleaned from Table 4, the result shows that in educational attainment, there is a significant difference in the extent of awareness of teachers of the current trend and practices in the teaching profession ($F=13.905$; $p=0.00$), thereby rejecting the null hypothesis.

Table 4: ANOVA results of differences in the extent of awareness of teachers of current trends and practices in the teaching profession when grouped according to their educational attainment and length of service

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value
Educational Attainment					
Between Group	4.81	3	1.60	13.91	0.00*
Within Group	36.45	316	0.11		
Length of Service					
Between Group	0.55	2	0.27	2.13	0.21 ^{ns}
Within Group	40.72	317	0.13		

*.significant ($p < 0.05$); ns-not significant ($p > 0.05$)

This result means that teachers vary in how aware they are of the current trends and practices of the teaching profession. The finding of the study supports the findings of Bedan (2003) and Ampong (2009) that the higher the educational attainment of teachers, the better the level of awareness.

On the other hand, the ANOVA result revealed that there was no significant difference in the extent of awareness of the teachers of the current trends and practices in the teaching profession when they were grouped as to the length of service ($F=2.13$; $p=0.21$). This suggests that the number of years of stay in school does not influence their extent of awareness. This finding contradicts the findings of Gualberto (2002), which stipulates that the level of awareness of trends and issues of people is directly proportional to their length of service in the organization where they are working.

Post Hoc Test for Significant Difference in the Extent of Awareness of Teachers as to Educational Attainment

Since significant differences were found in the extent of awareness of teachers as to educational attainment, a posteriori test was employed using Scheffe's method to find out where the differences lie, as shown in Table 5 below.

The data showed that differences were found between the BS degree holder and master's degree holders, the BS degree holders and those with PhD or EdD units, those with master's units and the master's degree holders, the teachers with master's units and those with PhD or EdD units. It suggests that differences in the extent of awareness of teachers are found between those with lower educational attainment and higher educational attainment.

Table 5: Post Hoc Test results for the significant difference in the extent of awareness of teachers as to their educational attainment

Educational Attainment			Mean Difference	p-value
BS degree	vs	with Master's units	0.112	0.54 ^{ns}
		Master's degree	0.406	0.00*
		with PhD/EdD units	0.445	0.00*
With Master's units	vs	BS degree	0.112	0.54 ^{ns}
		Master's degree	0.295	0.00*
		with PhD/EdD units	0.333	0.03*
Master's degree	vs	BS degree	0.406	0.00*
		with Master's units	0.295	0.00*
		with PhD/EdD units	0.036	0.99 ^{ns}

*.significant ($p < 0.05$); ns-not significant ($p > 0.05$)

Table 6: T-test results of differences in the extent of awareness of teachers of current trends and practices in the teaching profession when grouped according to their educational level taught and sex

Category	Mean	df	t-test	p-value
Educational Level Taught				
Secondary	2.79	318	1.85	0.06 ^{ns}
Elementary	2.87			
Sex				
Male	3.15	318	0.56	0.96 ^{ns}
Female	3.16			

*.significant ($p < 0.05$); ns-not significant ($p > 0.05$)

When the mean scores of the teachers in the extent of awareness were further tested for the significant difference when they were grouped as to educational level taught and sex, the t-test was used. It can be gleaned from Table 6 that there is no significant difference existed in the extent of awareness of elementary and secondary

teachers ($t=1.85$; $p=0.06$), thereby failing to reject the null hypothesis. This means that whether teachers are in elementary or secondary schools does not affect their awareness of trends and practices of the teaching profession.

The same could be said when the teachers were grouped

as to sex. There is no significant difference in the extent of awareness of teachers ($t=0.056$; $p=0.96$). This finding is consistent with Palangdao (2009) and Cisnero (2010), claiming that males and females do not differ in their awareness of trends and practices in the teaching profession.

Test of Differences Between the Extent of Commitment to Work of Teachers and their Profile Variables

Tables 7 to 9 display the test of significant differences in the extent of commitment to work of teachers when grouped according to their profile variables.

Table 7: ANOVA results of differences in the extent of commitment to work of teachers when grouped according to their educational attainment and length of service

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value
Educational Attainment					
Between Group	1.05	3	0.35	3.56	0.02*
Within Group	31.11	316	0.10		
Length of Service					
Between Group	0.13	2	0.07	0.64	0.53 ^{ns}
Within Group	32.03	317	0.10		

*-significant ($p<0.05$); ns-not significant ($p>0.05$)

When significant differences in the extent of the commitment of teachers were tested, the ANOVA result shows that in educational attainment, significant differences were found favoring the teachers with higher educational qualifications ($F=3.53$; $p=0.02$). This finding concurs with the findings of Raju and Srivastara (1994), which showed that teachers with higher educational status are more committed to their work.

On the other hand, when the teachers were grouped as to the length of service, it was revealed that there were no significant differences that existed in the commitment of teachers ($F=0.64$; $p=0.53$). This suggests that the extent of the commitment of teachers who are longer in service

does not depart from the commitment of teachers who are new in the service. This finding differs from the study of Sood and Anand (2010) in that those who stayed longer in the service have a better commitment to their profession.

Post Hoc Test for the Extent of Commitment of Teachers When They are Grouped as to Educational Attainment

Since there were significant differences in the commitment of teachers to their educational attainment, a post hoc test was conducted using Scheffe's method, as shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Post Hoc Test results for the significant difference in the extent of commitment to work of teachers as to their educational attainment

Educational Attainment			Mean Difference	p-value
BS degree	vs	with Master's units	0.050	0.60 ^{ns}
		Master's degree	0.138	0.28 ^{ns}
		with PhD/EdD units	0.285	0.05*
With Master's units	vs	BS degree	0.050	0.60 ^{ns}
		Master's degree	0.088	0.67 ^{ns}
		with PhD/EdD units	0.230	0.70 ^{ns}
Master's degree	vs	BS degree	0.139	0.28 ^{ns}
		with Master's units	0.088	0.67 ^{ns}
		with PhD/EdD units	0.142	0.70 ^{ns}

*-significant ($p<0.05$); ns-not significant ($p>0.05$)

It shows the only difference between the BS degree holders and those with PhD or EdD units. This suggests that the commitment of teachers differs between the

teachers with the lowest educational attainment and the highest educational attainment.

When the significant difference in the commitment of

Table 9: T-test results of differences in the extent of commitment to work of teachers when grouped according to their educational level taught and sex

Category	Mean	df	t-test	p-value
Educational Level Taught				
Secondary	3.13	318	1.68	0.09 ^{ns}
Elementary	3.19			
Sex				
Male	3.15	318	0.21	0.83 ^{ns}
Female	3.16			

*-significant ($p<0.05$); ns-not significant ($p>0.05$)

teachers was further tested using educational level taught as the grouping variable, the t-test result showed no significant difference in the commitment of elementary and secondary school teachers ($t=1.68$; $p=0.09$). This means that the elementary teachers in the Division of Antique are as committed and passionate as the secondary teachers in their work.

As to the sex of the teachers, the t-test result showed no significant difference in the commitment of male and female teachers ($t=0.21$; $p=0.83$). This means that the male teachers are as committed as the female teachers. This finding contradicts the findings of Shapira-Lischshinsky (2009) and Hussain et al. (2011), who reported that female teachers are more committed than male teachers.

CONCLUSIONS

Given the study findings, the researchers disclosed that the teachers in the Division of Antique are aware of the trends and practices in the teaching profession. They understand the programs and agenda instituted by the Department of Education and the works called for by these programs and agenda. Further, teachers are committed and passionate about their work. They have the zeal and enthusiasm to carry out the many works and obligations expected of them. Results also showed that educational attainment affects the commitment of teachers. Teachers with higher educational attainment are more committed to their profession. On the other hand, length of service, educational level taught, and sex does not affect the commitment of teachers. Teachers with higher educational attainment teach better than teachers with lower academic qualifications. Teachers who have longer years of service likewise teach better than those who are new in the service. Educational level taught and sex does not affect the teaching performance of teachers. Moreover, teachers' awareness of current trends and practices in the teaching profession and commitment to the profession is associated with teaching performance the teachers. Therefore, the higher the awareness of teachers, the more open they are to change, and the more committed they are, the better their teaching performance and the work and obligations that might be given to them in response to the changes in the educational system.

Acknowledgment

The researchers would like to extend their gratitude to the Schools Division Superintendent, district supervisors, and school heads for allowing them to conduct the study. Most especially to the teachers who have shared their time in answering the survey questionnaire.

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